

The First General Zagreb Index and Some Hamiltonian Properties of Graphs

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Abstract

The first general Zagreb index of a graph G is defined as the sum of the α th powers of the vertex degrees of G , where α is a real number such that $\alpha \neq 0$ and $\alpha \neq 1$. Using the first general Zagreb index with $\alpha > 1$, we present sufficient conditions for Hamiltonian and traceable of graphs.

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1 Introduction

We consider only finite undirected graphs without loops or multiple edges. Notation and terminology not defined here follow those in [1]. Let $G = (V(G), E(G))$ be a graph with n vertices and e edges, the degree of a vertex v is denoted by $d(v)$. We use δ to denote the minimum degree of G . A set of vertices in a graph G is independent if the vertices in the set are pairwise nonadjacent. A maximum independent set in a graph G is an independent

set of largest possible size. The independence number, denoted $\beta(G)$, of a graph G is the cardinality of a maximum independent set in G . A cycle C in a graph G is called a Hamiltonian cycle of G if C contains all the vertices of G . A graph G is called Hamiltonian if G has a Hamiltonian cycle. A path P in a graph G is called a Hamiltonian path of G if P contains all the vertices of G . A graph G is called traceable if G has a Hamiltonian path.

The first Zagreb index was introduced by Gutman and Trinajstić in [3]. For a graph G , its first Zagreb index is defined as $\sum_{v \in V(G)} d_G^2(v)$. Li and Zheng in [6] further extended the first Zagreb index of a graph and introduced the concept of the first general Zagreb index of a graph. The first general Zagreb index, denoted $M_\alpha(G)$, of a graph G is defined as $\sum_{v \in V(G)} d_G^\alpha(v)$, where α is a real number such that $\alpha \neq 0$ and $\alpha \neq 1$.

Li in [5] obtained the following lower bound for the first general Zagreb index of a graph with $\alpha > 1$.

Theorem 1. Let G be a graph with n vertices and e edges. Assume α is a real number such that $\alpha > 1$. Then

$$M_\alpha \geq \beta \delta^\alpha + \frac{e^\alpha}{(n - \beta)^{\alpha-1}}.$$

Equality holds if and only if G is a graph satisfying the following conditions. For any maximum independent set I in G , $d(u) = \delta$ if $u \in I$, $V - I$ is independent and $d(v) = \delta_1 \geq \delta$ if $v \in V - I$, and $e = \beta \delta = (n - \beta) \delta_1$.

Using the above lower for the first general Zagreb index of a graph with $\alpha > 1$, we in this note present sufficient conditions based on the first general Zagreb index of a graph with $\alpha > 1$ for the Hamiltonian and traceable graphs. The main results are as follows.

Theorem 2. Let G be a k -connected ($k \geq 2$) graph with $n \geq 3$ vertices and e edges. Assume α is a real number such that $\alpha > 1$. If

$$M_\alpha \leq (k + 1) \delta^\alpha + \frac{e^\alpha}{(n - k - 1)^{\alpha-1}},$$

then G is Hamiltonian or $K_{k, k+1}$.

Theorem 3. Let G be a k -connected ($k \geq 2$) with $n \geq 12$ vertices and e edges. Assume α is a real number such that $\alpha > 1$. If

$$M_\alpha \leq (k+2)\delta^\alpha + \frac{e^\alpha}{(n-k-2)^{\alpha-1}},$$

then G is traceable or $K_{k,k+2}$.

2 Lemmas

We will use the following results as our lemmas. The first two are from [2].

Lemma 1 [2]. Let G be a k -connected graph of order $n \geq 3$. If $\beta \leq k$, then G is Hamiltonian.

Lemma 2 [2]. Let G be a k -connected graph of order n . If $\beta \leq k+1$, then G is traceable.

Lemma 3 below is from [7].

Lemma 3 [7]. Let G be a balanced bipartite graph of order $2n$ with bipartition (A, B) . If $d(x) + d(y) \geq n+1$ for any $x \in A$ and any $y \in B$ with $xy \notin E$, then G is Hamiltonian.

Lemma 4 below is from [4].

Lemma 4 [4]. Let G be a 2-connected bipartite graph with bipartition (A, B) , where $|A| \geq |B|$. If each vertex in A has degree at least s and each vertex in B has degree at least t , then G contains a cycle of length at least $2 \min(|B|, s+t-1, 2s-2)$.

3 Proofs

Proof of Theorem 2. Let G be a graph satisfying the conditions in Theorem 2. Suppose G is not Hamiltonian. Then Lemma 1 implies that $\beta \geq k+1$. Also, we have that $n \geq 2\delta + 1 \geq 2k + 1$ otherwise $\delta \geq k \geq n/2$ and G is Hamiltonian. Let $I := \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_\beta\}$ be a maximum independent set. By

Theorem 1, we have that

$$(k + 1)\delta^\alpha + \frac{e^\alpha}{(n - k - 1)^{\alpha-1}} \geq M_\alpha \geq \beta\delta^\alpha + \frac{e^\alpha}{(n - \beta)^{\alpha-1}} \geq (k + 1)\delta^\alpha + \frac{e^\alpha}{(n - k - 1)^{\alpha-1}}.$$

Thus

$$M_\alpha = \beta\delta^\alpha + \frac{e^\alpha}{(n - \beta)^{\alpha-1}}, \beta = k + 1.$$

By Theorem 1 again, we have $d(u_1) = d(u_2) = \dots = d(u_\beta) = \delta$, $V - I$ is independent, $d(v) := \delta_1 \geq \delta$ if $v \in V - I$, $e = \beta\delta = (n - \beta)\delta_1$, and $\beta = k + 1$. Since $n \geq 2k + 1$, we just need to consider the following possible cases.

If $n \geq 2k + 3$, then $(k + 1)\delta = \beta\delta = (n - \beta)\delta_1 \geq (n - k - 1)\delta \geq (k + 2)\delta$, a contradiction.

If $n = 2k + 2$, then $(k + 1)\delta = \beta\delta = (n - \beta)\delta_1 \geq (n - k - 1)\delta \geq (k + 1)\delta$. Thus $\delta = \delta_1 \geq k$. By Lemma 3, we have that G is Hamiltonian, a contradiction.

If $n = 2k + 1$, then $|V - I| = 2k + 1 - \beta = 2k + 1 - k - 1 = k$. Since $d(u_1) = d(u_2) = \dots = d(u_\beta) = \delta \geq k$, we have that each vertex in I and each vertex in $(V - I)$ are adjacent. Thus G is $K_{k, k+1}$

This completes the proofs of Theorem 2.

Proof of Theorem 3. Let G be a graph satisfying the conditions in Theorem 3. Suppose G is not traceable graph. Then Lemma 2 implies that $\beta \geq k + 2$. Also, we have $n \geq 2\delta + 2 \geq 2k + 2$ otherwise $\delta \geq k \geq (n - 1)/2$ and G is traceable. Let $I := \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_\beta\}$ be a maximum independent set. By Theorem 1, we have that

$$(k + 2)\delta^\alpha + \frac{e^\alpha}{(n - k - 2)^{\alpha-1}} \geq M_\alpha \geq \beta\delta^\alpha + \frac{e^\alpha}{(n - \beta)^{\alpha-1}} \geq (k + 2)\delta^\alpha + \frac{e^\alpha}{(n - k - 2)^{\alpha-1}}.$$

Thus

$$M_\alpha = \beta\delta^\alpha + \frac{e^\alpha}{(n-\beta)^{\alpha-1}}, \quad \beta = k+2.$$

By Theorem 1 again, we have $d(u_1) = d(u_2) = \dots = d(u_\beta) = \delta$, $V - I$ is independent, $d(v) := \delta_1 \geq \delta$ if $v \in V - I$, $e = \beta\delta = (n - \beta)\delta_1$, and $\beta = k + 2$. Since $n \geq 2k + 2$, we just need to consider the following possible cases.

If $n \geq 2k + 5$, then $(k + 2)\delta = \beta\delta = (n - \beta)\delta_1 \geq (n - k - 2)\delta \geq (k + 3)\delta$, a contradiction.

If $n = 2k + 4$, then $2k + 4 = n \geq 12$ and $k \geq 4$. Notice that the degree of each vertex in I and $V - I$ is at least $\delta \geq k$. By Lemma 3, we have that G has a cycle of length $2k + 4$, which implies G is traceable, a contradiction.

If $n = 2k + 3$, then $(k + 2)\delta = \beta\delta = (n - \beta)\delta_1 \geq (n - k - 2)\delta \geq (k + 2)\delta$. Thus $\delta = \delta_1 \geq k$. Since $2k + 3 = n \geq 12$, we have that $k \geq 5$. By Lemma 4, we have that G has a cycle of length at least $2k + 2$. Since $n = 2k + 3$ and $k \geq 5$, there exists a path in G containing all the vertices of G . Thus G is traceable, a contradiction.

If $n = 2k + 2$, then $|V - I| = 2k + 2 - \beta = 2k + 2 - k - 2 = k$. Since $d(u_1) = d(u_2) = \dots = d(u_\beta) = \delta \geq k$, we have that each vertex in I and each vertex in $(V - I)$ are adjacent. Thus G is $K_{k, k+2}$.

This completes the proofs of Theorem 3.

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